

TWO FOLK POETS

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Abstract: In his poetic work, Shaykhzoda shook a pen, mainly on modern topics, and in his dramaturgy, he gave a fresh artistic life to the siymos and events that help to shed light on the modern problems in it, giving a thoughtful look at the historical past.

Keywords: poetic work, poetry collections, literary critic.

The son of Maqsud Maqsumbek, Shaykhzoda Maqsud Shaikhzoda was born in the city of Oqtosh, Ganja region, Republic of Azerbaijan (1908.25.10 — 1967.19.2, Tashkent) — poet, playwright, literary critic, translator, educator. Honored Artist of Uzbekistan (1964). Graduated from doril-teacher in Baku (1925). Initially, he worked as a teacher at the L-stage Azerbaijani school in Darband, the Technical School of Education and upbringing in Furs. He was arrested in 1927 as a member of the counter-revolutionary organization and exiled to Tashkent in February 1928. After a short period of study at the Oriental Faculty of the Central Asian University, shaykhzoda served in the editorial offices of the newspapers "the truth of the East" (1929-1932), 'Red Uzbekistan', "yosh leninchi" (1932), "Gulistan" magazine (1933-1934). In 1933, he passed the exam for all courses of the Pedagogical Institute in Baku and entered graduate school under the Science Committee (1934).

An early poetic collection is "the worthy watchman" (1933). This was followed by his city's "ten poems" (1932), "my consonants" (1933), "book Three" (1934), "Republic" (1935), "twelve", "new devon" (1937), "election songs" (1938), "wrestling nechun?"(1942), "Battle and song", "Heart says" (1943), "a notebook of

fifteen years" (1947), "poems of the land" (1948), "the strings of time", "my applause" (1949), "years and roads" (1961), "Poems" (1964), and other poetry collections have been published. In the early work of Shahi, and in part in some of his poems of the 50s, melodies characteristic of Azerbaijani poetry, signs of pulpit poetry were prioritized. But as the Shaykhzoda acquired the language and style of Uzbek classical and modern poetry, the Uzbek musical fluency in his poems went to kuchaya. The sheikhzoda, striving to actively react to reality, paid special attention to the description of important events that took place in the life of the people and the country, the creation of the image of the heroes of Labor and struggle. To this end, he took the epic genre, writing "uncle property" (1933), "the lamp", "Uncle", "inheritance", "soil and truth" (1936), "the Hunter's tale", "Iskandar Zulqarnayn" (1940), "the eleven", "Jenya", "The Elder" (1943), "the wisdom of Akhmadjan", "the third son" (1944), "the dream of the Nurmat father" (1944) 1947), and wrote liroepic works. One of the important qualities inherent in both the poet's poetry of the 30s and 40s and his subsequent work is plot. As a poet inclined to create a lyrical plot, shaykhzoda turned to the pages of folk legends and historical past, as well as the lives of contemporaries, bringing to his poems poetic characters and various poetic details characteristic of the ballad, taking measures to increase the position of the word in the poetic device. This principle inherent in the work of the poet was vividly expressed in his, especially in the lyrical epic "Tashkent" (1958).

Shaikhzoda's tragedy "Jaloliddin Manguberdi" (1944), written during the years of World War 2, historically accurately and truthfully described the martial courage of the last Khwarezmian King, who fought against the Mughal invaders for the freedom and independence of his land. In the tragedy "Mirzo Ulugbek" (1961), Shaykhzoda embodied the image of the main character as a vivid embodiment of the awakening that took place in the life of the Uzbek people during the reign of Amir Timur and the Timurids. Written in a Shakespearean style, the work also truthfully depicts the last 2 years of Shaikhzoda Ulughbek's life as a distinguished scholar, a

righteous and truthful statesman, and at the same time a helpless man before the fanatical forces of the kingdom. The arrival on the field of the tragedy "Mirzo Ulugbek", written with Shakespearean scope and temperature, was a big event in the history of Uzbek drama and theater. From a screenplay by Shaykhzoda, it was directed by L. The film "star of Ulugbek" (1964), created by Fayziev, on the other hand, allowed the general public to get acquainted with the great Uzbek scientist and his tragic.

In his poetic work, Shaykhzoda shook a pen, mainly on modern topics, and in his dramaturgy, he gave a fresh artistic life to the siymos and events that help to shed light on the modern problems in it, giving a thoughtful look at the historical past. In the last years of his life, he wrote his last stage play about Berunius.

Shaykhzoda not only wrote works in all types and genres of artistic creation, but also effectively created as a literary critic and critic. Until the last days of his life, Shaykhzadeh, who published the monograph "general poet" as early as 1941, was constantly engaged in the life and work of Navoi. After the article "on the lyrical hero of Navoi" (1948), which he wrote on the occasion of the 500th anniversary of Navoi, he created major scientific studies "on some poetic methods of Navoi lyricism" (1959), "in the Art Room of the Master" (3-part article, 1965-66), "the Sultan of the ghazal estate" (1966), "from the history of As a literary critic and critic, shaikhzade also shook an effective pen, became a famous poet of Uzbek folk oral creativity, works such as" Alpomish", "sugar with sugar", Babur, Muqimiy, Furqat, Oybek, Ghafur Ghulam, Hamid Olimjon, Nizami Ganjavii of world literature, Sh. Rustaveli, A.S. Pushkin, N.A. Nekrasov, A.N. Ostrovsky, T.G. Shevchenko, A.P. Like Chekhov, he wrote works dedicated to his manifestations.

Translation played an important role in the expansion of the sphere of literary knowledge of the sheikhzoda, the enrichment of his work with the artistic experience of classical world writers. He is the author of Shota Rustaveli's (collaborative) epic "The paxlavon covering the skin of a tiger", Shakespeare's sonnets, A.S. Poems by

Pushkin, epic "The Copper rider", tragedy "Mozart and Salieri", M.Yu. Lermontov's poems and the epic "prisoner of the Caucasus" also translated with great skill into Uzbek. The Works of Nizami, Fuzuli, Mirza Fatali Okhundov, Ezop, Aeschylus, Goethe, Byron, Mayakovsky, Nozim Hikmat and some other writers.

The hero of Uzbekistan Azad Sharofiddinov writes in the article “dedication of our literature” dedicated to Maqsud Shaykhzoda: “this man – Shaykhzoda Maqsud, who is of medium height, has a large figure, curly hair somehow poetically straightened, pronounces Uzbek words in an Azerbaijani sweet tone. Although we were looking closely at him for the first time, his dowry was already scattered throughout Uzbekistan, leaving the territories of the Pedagogical Institute named after Nizami, where he works. His lectures were narrated among the students.

” The Genial artist " was hijacked. The book, published in Latin script, was one of four critical works available on Alisher Navoi at the beginning of the 40s. This treatise, written with great ingenuity, was watered with such love by Alisher Navoi that any person who read it could not feel the genius of Navoi with his heart and indulge in his miraculous art for life”.

Shukur Burhonov: "brother Sheikh lived the perfect life. This life, although years, centuries pass, continues to be exemplified. He would have a cordial relationship with everyone. He himself was a handsome man, very good - natured. Always correct, often something in his statements of course acquired a hidden meaning. Maqsud taught, wrote works and poems in the editorial office. We were envious that he could get along quickly with any person. There was a distinct philosophy in his conversations. My younger son was also named by him as Shavkat.”

But later, the hero of the Sheikhzoda in the work “Jaloliddin Manguberdi” in the image of a negative Georgian is exiled to Siberia for 25 years, allegedly referring to Stalin and the Georgian people. After Stalin's death in 1952, Shaykhzoda's mother sent a series of letters to the Presidium of the Supreme Soviet of the USSR requesting

the pardon of her son, proving his innocence. Knowing that he is also innocent, the executioners of the Empire send the Sheik back to Tashkent after serving a third of his sentence. Many of his friends stop saluting the Sheikhzō. They withdraw from him as much as possible. The poet suffers from this spiritually. At the same time, will continue to create. Chala completes the rest of the tragedy" Treasure Of Glory". Based on the work, Uzbek director Latif Fayziyev will make the 1958 film "star of Ulugbek". The Film will gain great fame. He also writes The Epic "Tashkent". Thus the poet's former position is restored.

Academician Naim Karimov writes that the poet, having returned from exile ill, is periodically forced to undergo treatment. For a long time, he sweats over the work" Abu Rayhon Beruniy", but ajal does not allow him to finish the work.

Why were the questions addressed to the teachers in writing?

Mirzakalon Ismaili, a writer and translator who studied with Maqsud Shaykhzadeh, writes in his memoirs:

"Maqsud spoke Uzbek in the Azeri dialect. He actively used Azeri and Turkish words. He had great respect among the students for his deep Savoie and human qualities. Maqsud had learned Uzbek language, history, eastern culture with enthusiasm and reverence. As soon as the lessons ended, they began to prepare for tomorrow, read books, write synopsis, put up books related to subsequent topics, questions to teachers. He would ask the questions to the teachers in writing, which was interesting to domlamiz Mukhtar Avezov. When Maqsud found out why she asked her questions in writing, domlamiz was lol. Maqsud when asking questions in writing so that the teacher does not know the answer to the question, so as not to remain in an uncomfortable situation in the face of other students."

Journalist Gulu Kengerli's "The Forgotten Past becomes history" again cites the following information:

Maqsud Shaykhzadeh has always helped students. When a student saw that his clothes were worn out, he did not have a coat or telpagi, he would of course smoke

50 or 100 s in his hand and send them to a cigarette. When the student took a cigarette and brought it to him, domla would say, “go and get some clothes for yourself.” Adib died in a hospital in Tashkent in 1967. He is buried in the Phorobius Cemetery in Tashkent.

The chala manuscript of "Abu Raykhan Beruniy" disappears in the hospital. The Life Book of Maqsud Shaikhzoda, whom the younger ones call “Shaikh aka”, the adult “Shaikh”, thus ends.

But reverence for the work of Shaykxzoda, a great scientist, singer and devotee of the Uzbek language, lives in the hearts of every Uzbek creator and child. Even after his death, tomlik's works were published. By decree of our first president Islam Karimov, adib was awarded the order of Merit.

The Uzbek people's writer Shukrullo called Shaykxzoda "Shakespeare of Uzbek literature". After all, his great services for the Uzbek language – translations of Uzbek works into Azeri, Russian and Azeri works into Uzbek, Uzbek prose works, poems and epics-deserve this definition. Maqsud Shaykxzoda siyma has become a symbol of friendship, brotherhood, enlightenment, spirituality, goodness for the peoples of Uzbekistan and Azerbaijan, and will continue to be so further.

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